

Local Government in Croatia

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

Dario Runtic

NALAS - Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South-East Europe
with the support of the Association of Cities in the Republic of Croatia

Partners

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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INFORMATION

Eurac Research
Viale Druso/Drususallee, 1
39100 Bolzano/Bozen – Italy

logov@eurac.edu
www.logov-rise.eu

SCIENTIFIC COORDINATION

Eurac Research: Karl Kössler

WP 1 – Local Responsibilities and Public Services

LMU Munich: Martin Burgi

WP 2 – Local Financial Arrangements

Universidad Autónoma de Madrid: Francisco Velasco Caballero

WP 3 – Structure of Local Government

University of Fribourg: Eva Maria Belser

WP 4 – Intergovernmental Relations of Local Government

NALAS – Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South East Europe: Elton Stafa

WP 5 – People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making

Ximpulse GmbH: Erika Schläppi

EDITORIAL TEAM

NALAS - Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South-East Europe with the support of the Association of Cities in the Republic of Croatia: Dario Runtic
Eurac Research: Karl Kössler, Theresia Morandell, Caterina Salvo, Annika Kress, Petra Malfertheiner

GRAPHIC DESIGN

Eurac Research: Alessandra Stefanut

COVER PHOTO

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1. The System of Local Government in Croatia

Dario Runtic, *NALAS Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South-East Europe*

Types of Local Governments

Croatia has 21 units of regional self-government (*zupanija*), 20 counties and the Croatian Capital City of Zagreb. Each county is divided into a number of local government units. Also, each county has its own representative and executive body elected by popular vote for a term of four years. The City of Zagreb is a special territorial and administrative unit whose responsibilities are regulated by a separate Act on the City of Zagreb. The City of Zagreb has a dual status as a unit of local and regional government unit and thus performs activities within the scope of the city and as a county. It also carries out responsibilities of the state administration. In doing so administrative bodies of the City of Zagreb have the powers and obligations of state administration bodies.

There are 556 units of local government, that is 128 towns (*grad*) and 428 municipalities (*opcina*). Towns are local government units typically of urban character with more than 10,000 inhabitants. Exceptions apply in case of historical, economic or geospatial reasons. Municipalities are local government units of rural character with less than 10,000 inhabitants. Each town and municipality has its own representative and executive body elected by popular vote for a term of four years. Each local government unit is further divided into one or more settlements regardless urban or rural. One or more settlements are represented by sub-local government entities called neighborhood councils with elected representatives which serve on non-professional terms. Some towns and some municipalities have only one neighborhood council. Towns and municipalities have basically the same responsibilities, except for towns in which counties have their administrative seat and towns with a population above 30,000 inhabitants. The latter are referred to as 'large towns' and have additional responsibilities. Seats of county are generally the largest towns within a county. There are only four large towns which are not the seat of a county.

Legal Status of Local Governments

The right to local and regional self-government is guaranteed by Article 128 of the Croatian Constitution, according to which '[c]itizens shall be guaranteed the right to local and regional self-government' and this right 'shall be exercised through local and/or regional representative bodies', as well as citizens' direct participation in the administration of local affairs.

The rights specified in this Article shall be exercised by Croatian and European Union nationals in compliance with law and EU *acquis communautaire*.

The right to local government is further prescribed in national legislation such as the general Local Government Act, Local Government Financing Act, etc. The Croatian system of local self-government is based on the principle of autonomy of government and the principle of subsidiarity. The European Charter of Local Self-Government has been fully ratified by the Croatian Parliament. Croatian local governments have a judicially enforceable right to local self-government before the Constitutional Court and other judiciary bodies.

(A) Symmetry of the Local Government System

Local authorities have comprehensive responsibilities which are enumerated in the Constitution and further prescribed by the general Local Government Act. Local government units perform tasks of local importance which directly affect needs of the citizens and which are not assigned to state bodies by the Constitution or other laws, and especially the tasks referring to organization of settlement and housing; spatial and urban planning; utility services; child-care; primary health protection; social welfare; elementary education; culture, physical culture and sports; consumer protection; environment protection; fire and civil protection; maintenance of municipal roads and traffic management. In addition to these competences, large towns also have responsibilities related to maintenance of local public roads and construction permits.

Regional government units carry out affairs of regional importance which are not assigned to central bodies by the Constitution or other laws. The scope of counties' responsibilities can be self-managing and entrusted (government affairs). Counties are tasked with performing the following tasks: general public administration services; primary and secondary education; healthcare; regional and urban planning; economic development; environmental protection; transport and traffic infrastructure; management of the network of educational, medical, social welfare, and cultural institutions; administration pertaining to agriculture, forestry, mining, and industry; management of road transport infrastructure; construction permitting, excluding the area of big cities and a county seat city.

Re-assignment of responsibilities between individual local and regional governments is allowed pending approval of the representative bodies of both government units. Out of 556 local government units some 8-10 local governments have taken over such responsibilities. Certain restrictions apply such as the ability to fund a specific responsibility (in case of most of responsibilities) and a minimum number of inhabitants (8,000 inhabitants for management of elementary education).

Political and Social Context in Croatia

The Croatian population of 4.2 million is predominantly urban with 71 per cent of the total population living in towns which cover 39 per cent of total territory. The remaining 29 per cent of the total population are scattered through municipalities which cover 61 per cent of Croatian territory. According to the 2011 Census, 19 per cent of the population lives in Zagreb, the capital city of Croatia. Population density is 76 inhabitants per square kilometer (139 inhabitants per square kilometer in towns, 36 in municipalities).

National parties dominate local level of government. In 2009, direct elections of a mayor were used for the first time, replacing the former system in which a representative body elected a mayor. But this did not significantly change the political landscape at the local level. The share of incumbents who lost in the 2017 elections was 40 per cent in towns and 30 per cent in municipalities, but national parties still dominate local level of government. In the 2017 elections a group of non-aligned mayors raised, making them the second largest 'political' group at the local level with a share of 15 per cent of the total number of town/municipal mayors.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Legal Documents:

Constitution of the Republic of Croatia, 2014

Law no 110/2015 on Territories of Counties, Cities and Municipalities

Law no 98/2019 on Local and Regional Self-Government

Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications:

Ministry of Administration of the Republic of Croatia, 'Local and territorial (regional) Self-Government' <<https://uprava.gov.hr/o-ministarstvu/ustrojstvo/5-uprava-za-politicki-sustav-i-organizaciju-uprave-1075/lokalna-i-podrucna-regionalna-samouprava/842>>

Contacts

Local Government and the Changing
Urban-Rural Interplay
www.logov-rise.eu
logov@eurac.edu

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